

ISic3678

Fragment of a Greek inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

unknown

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe

Autopsy

2017-07-24

Last Change

2019-07-23 - Jonathan Prag edited file on basis of autopsy and photograph 2017

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Found in summer 1956 in trench 31 (5-10m east of the 'east portico', see Carettoni, NSA 1959, fig.8)

Coordinates

37.998108, 14.263053

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa

Physical Description

Two small joining fragments of an off-white marble plaque, of which the top margin is preserved, but broken on left, right and below. The reverse is only roughly finished.

Dimensions

Height 8.5 cm

Width 10 cm

Depth not measured cm

Layout

The remains of two lines of Greek letters are preserved, with a small border of white space above; the second line is only partially preserved; the beginning and end of both lines is missing.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Relatively tall and thin letters with short serifs: alpha with straight bar; kappa with full length, lightly curving tail; rho with small closed eye;

Letter heights:

Line 1: 36 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 7 mm

Text

1. [---]κapp[---]

2. [---]λ,λ,ρ[---]

Apparatus

text from autopsy

Carettoni: KAPPI[--]

Carettoni: .ΛCI[--]

Translation

Commentary

An upward left-right sloping hasta is visible before the first lambda of line 2, which must be part of one of kappa, upsilon, or chi. Carettoni's reading of lunate sigma in line 2 seems implausible as the stroke extends round on the right side as far as the stone survives. Traces of another letter are visible at the end of both lines. The form of the letters strongly suggests an imperial date, as does the use of marble. A couple of rare names begin in KAPP, otherwise the letters may conceivably be from a form of κάρρων

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 311 no.12b

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